

BARRIERS TO THE INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF DISTANCE EDUCATION: AN ANALYSIS OF ACADEMIC SCHOLARSHIP*

OBSTÁCULOS AO PROCESSO DE INSTITUCIONALIZAÇÃO DA EAD: ANÁLISE DA PRODUÇÃO ACADÊMICA

OBSTÁCULOS AL PROCESO DE INSTITUCIONALIZACIÓN DE LA EDUCACIÓN A DISTANCIA: ANÁLISIS DE LA PRODUCCIÓN ACADÉMICA

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ABSTRACT. The expansion of Distance Education (DE) as an educational mode has posed challenges regarding the quality of instruction provided to students. It is posited that the issue of quality in distance education may be partially attributed to its institutionalization process within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This study aimed to identify the main challenges faced during the institutionalization process by examining academic scholarship—specifically doctoral dissertations and master's theses—that analyzed this phenomenon across various HEIs. Methodologically, a qualitative literature review was conducted, utilizing a search in the Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) using the search terms "Institucionalização da EaD" or "Institucionalização da Educação a Distância" (Institutionalization of DE). A total of 33 documents were selected (10 doctoral dissertations and 23 master's theses), the majority of which (94%) originated from graduate programs at public institutions. Bibliometric analysis revealed a concentration of works produced between 2014 and 2019. Twenty-six obstacles to institutionalization were identified and categorized into seven specific groups, ranging from faculty development, regulation of the modality, and stigma, to infrastructure and funding issues impacting DE in Brazil. It is concluded that the research field regarding the institutionalization of DE is well-established. Furthermore, the understanding that this process transcends administrative aspects, constituting a truly pedagogical endeavor, remains fundamental.

Keywords: Institutionalization. Challenges. Higher Education. Quality of DE. Funding.

RESUMO. O crescimento da Educação a Distância (EaD) enquanto modalidade educacional vem se provando desafiador no que diz respeito à qualidade do ensino oferecido aos estudantes. Acreditamos que parte do problema da qualidade da educação a distância pode estar associada ao seu processo de institucionalização nas instituições de ensino superior. O presente trabalho buscou identificar os principais desafios enfrentados no processo de institucionalização a partir da produção acadêmica, teses e dissertações, que a analisaram em diversas instituições de ensino superior. A metodologia empregou um estudo qualitativo de revisão da literatura, realizando um levantamento no Banco Digital de Teses e Dissertações (BDTD) por meio dos termos “Institucionalização da EaD” ou “Institucionalização da Educação a Distância”. Foram selecionados 33 documentos (10 teses e 23 dissertações), sendo a maioria (94%) oriunda de programas de pós-graduação de instituições públicas. A análise bibliométrica revelou uma concentração de produções entre 2014 e 2019. Identificamos 26 obstáculos à institucionalização que foram agrupados em 7 categorias específicas, indicando desde elementos da formação docente, regulamentação da modalidade, preconceitos, questões de infraestrutura e financiamento que impactam a EaD no Brasil. Conclui-se que o campo de pesquisa sobre a institucionalização da EaD é bem consolidado, e a compreensão de que esse processo vai além do administrativo, configurando-se como verdadeiramente pedagógico, permanece fundamental.

Palavras-chave: Institucionalização. Desafios. Ensino Superior. Qualidade da EaD. Financiamento.

RESUMEN. El crecimiento de la Educación a Distancia (EaD) como modalidad educativa ha demostrado ser desafiante en lo que respecta a la calidad de la enseñanza ofrecida a los estudiantes. Creemos que parte del problema de la calidad de la educación a distancia puede estar asociado a su proceso de institucionalización en las instituciones de educación superior. El presente trabajo buscó identificar los principales desafíos enfrentados en el proceso de institucionalización a partir de la producción académica, tesis y disertaciones, que la analizaron en diversas instituciones de educación superior. La metodología empleó un estudio cualitativo de revisión de la literatura, realizando una búsqueda en el Banco Digital de Tesis y Disertaciones (BDTD) a través de los términos "Institucionalización de la EaD" o "Institucionalización de la Educación a Distancia". Se seleccionaron 33 documentos (10 tesis y 23 disertaciones), la mayoría (94%) proveniente de programas de posgrado de instituciones públicas. El análisis bibliométrico reveló una concentración de producciones entre 2014 y 2019. Identificamos 26 obstáculos para la institucionalización que se agruparon en 7 categorías específicas, que abarcan desde elementos de formación docente, regulación de la modalidad, prejuicios, cuestiones de infraestructura y financiamiento que impactan la EaD en Brasil. Se concluye que el campo de investigación sobre la institucionalización de la EaD está bien consolidado, y la comprensión de que este proceso va más allá de lo administrativo, configurándose como verdaderamente pedagógico, sigue siendo fundamental.

Palabras clave: Institucionalización. Desafíos. Educación superior. Calidad de la educación a distancia. Financiamento.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Distance Education (DE) in Brazil has reached significant figures in recent decades, becoming the educational modality with the highest growth in student enrollment, course offerings, and vacancies in higher education, according to data from the Higher Education Census (DEED, 2024). However, DE does not present itself as a pre-defined model to be merely adopted by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs); rather, it stands as a distinct modality that requires institutionalization.

To monitor this institutionalization process, which varies from one institution to another, many researchers have examined this theme. They have produced studies and analyses—in the form of doctoral dissertations and master's theses—regarding the challenges, the strategies employed to overcome them, and the cases of success and failure of universities and other HEIs in incorporating DE into their educational processes. Particularly in recent years, as attention has shifted toward the quality of instruction offered through the distance modality, understanding how this modality was inserted into the institution—how it was planned and effectively implemented—becomes a pathway to comprehending this quality (or the lack thereof) that is so frequently questioned.

This study aimed to analyze this body of academic scholarship, identifying the main challenges to the process of DE institutionalization. The contribution of this research is considered relevant to the current context of DE in Brazil, which is undergoing significant changes due to new legal regulations. Following this brief introduction, we will proceed to the methodological details and the discussion, concluding with final remarks.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study is characterized as qualitative research. Fundamentally, it consists of a literature review.

To identify the characteristics of the DE institutionalization process in Brazilian Higher Education Institutions, a survey was conducted in the Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) database. The search utilized the terms "Institucionalização da EaD" or "Institucionalização da Educação a Distância" (Institutionalization of DE), enclosed in quotation marks and separated by the Boolean operator "OR," without any time frame restrictions or other search refinements. The results yielded 33 documents (10 doctoral dissertations and 23 master's theses) which were included in the analysis. The majority (94%) originated from graduate programs at public higher education institutions, while 3% (1 work) came from a private university, and 3% (1 work) was linked to the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict/UFRJ).

Once the set of works for analysis was defined, we proceeded to read the texts to identify the elements indicated by their authors as problematic to the process of DE institutionalization. Through the creation of thematic clusters, which were refined following the analysis, we were able to group these elements into seven categories, as will be demonstrated subsequently. We also indicate in how many works each of these elements—which we termed "complicating factors"—is mentioned or can be identified.

3 DEVELOPMENT

The bibliometric analysis of the data reveals a concentration of scholarly output between 2014 and 2019, followed by a subsequent decline in the number of studies on the subject. This trend suggests a potential saturation of the research field. Figure 1 illustrates this information.

Figure 1 – Distribution of academic output by year of defense

Source: Created by the author, based on the research data.

Regarding the institutions with the highest number of studies, the Federal University of Goiás (UFG) stands out with four works, followed by the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), the Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar), and the University of Brasília (UNB), with three works each. The remaining works are distributed across various other institutions. Only one study originated from a state university (Unicamp), and, as previously mentioned, another pertains to a graduate program in private higher education.

4 RESULTS

In the context of DE, institutionalization appears to be much more than a mere act of formalization; it can be understood through the perspective of an interpretation made by the involved actors as a means to guide their social action (Souza, 2023). According to Bizarria (2014, p. 42), "the phenomenon [of institutionalization] reveals itself as a process emerging from social and interpersonal relations and from the shared meanings among the people who constitute the organization." Although institutionalizing is initially related to the context of internal and external regulations and compliance with these norms, the human role is considered essential (Bizarria, 2014; Chaquime, 2019; Marafante Sá, 2015; Moreira, 2021).

This conception transcends the merely bureaucratic. It suggests a true internalization of the modality (Souza, 2023), wherein DE ceases to be a "university ghetto" or a "voluntary and disharmonious act" by a few proponents to become an organic and respected part of the educational environment (Marafante Sá, 2015).

The importance of this process is, from many angles, undeniable. First, institutionalization is presented as a crucial element for the recognition and legitimation of DE in higher education (Marafante Sá, 2015; Souza, 2023). Historically, the modality has faced—and in many places still faces—cultural biases and skepticism. The act of institutionalizing helps build a collective identity that can overcome these fears (Marafante Sá, 2015), giving voice and presence to DE within the academy itself (Souza, 2023). Marafante Sá (2015) also indicates that, when properly executed, DE institutionalization promotes the quality, sustainability, and longevity of teaching, research, and outreach in this modality. It is not merely about expanding access—which is undoubtedly a merit of public policies encouraging DE, such as the Open University of Brazil (UAB) System—but about ensuring that this access is accompanied by excellence and social support (Marafante Sá, 2015).

To understand the nature of the DE institutionalization process, the majority of the studies examined (88%) employ Institutional Theory, Institutionalism, or Neo-institutionalism as an analytical framework or foundational theory applied to the study of the phenomenon. This theory appears to be the backbone for many studies seeking to understand how DE is established and gains legitimacy in public higher education (Chaquime, 2019). Regarding the data collection instruments identified in the works, they are listed in Table 1. An important observation is that a single study may utilize two or more data collection instruments. Bibliographic research was considered specifically when mentioned as a primary characteristic of the work, given that all research can be considered, to a greater or lesser extent, bibliographic research. In some works, the instrument(s) adopted for data collection were not clearly defined.

Table 1 – Data collection instruments

Data Collection Instrument	Distribution
Document/Archive Analysis	54.50%
Interviews	39.39%
Questionnaires	33.33%
Bibliographic Research / Literature Review	42.42%
Field Notes	06.00%
Virtual Ethnography	03.00%

Source: Created by the author, based on the research data.

The reviewed works presented indications of elements that hinder or make the DE institutionalization process impossible; these are synthesized in Table 2.

Table 2 – Complicating factors in the institutionalization process

Categories	Complicating Factors (Characteristics)	No. of Works
Cultural and Perceptual Barriers	Prejudice and Resistance to the Modality	13 works
	Lack of DE Culture	6 works
	Unfamiliarity with Specificities	4 works
	Invisibility and Marginalization	5 works
Structural and Organizational Challenges	Lack of Systemic Integration	7 works
	Bureaucracy and Slow Processes	3 works
	Inadequate Management and Planning Models	9 works
	Internal Disputes and Conflicts	5 works
	Lack of Role Clarity	4 works
Human Resources Issues	Insufficient or Unqualified Staff	8 works
	Precarization of Faculty and Tutor Work	9 works
	Deficient Faculty Training	6 works
Financial and Funding Constraints	Dependence on External Funding	13 works
	General Budgetary Constraints	13 works
	Absence of Dedicated Budget for DE	2 works
	Impact on Teaching, Research, and Outreach	4 works
Technological and Infrastructure Issues	Inadequate Physical and Technological Infrastructure	10 works
	Non-adapted Systems	4 works
	High Cost of Technology	1 work
Legal, Normative, and Policy Gaps	Lack of Clear Policies and Regulations	18 works
	Complex Legislation Under Construction	6 works
	Political and Administrative Uncertainties	6 works
	Lack of Specific Indicators	4 works
Inconsistency of Institutionalization	Slow and Incomplete Process	12 works
	Distinct and Unequal Phases	3 works
	Lack of Consistency	4 works

Source: Created by the author, based on the research data.

Research indicated that DE faces significant prejudice and institutional resistance, which hinders the integration of technology and the development of internal competencies (Macêdo, 2017; Marafante Sá, 2015). The process of persuading staff is arduous and protracted. There are attempts to keep UAB courses segregated from the university, driven by faculty fears regarding a potential decline in academic standards (Barrera, 2018).

Regarding human resources and staff qualification, difficulties were detected in staffing and retention due to a lack of permanent positions for technical and teaching staff, resulting in understaffing and disorganization (Calmeto, 2020). The instability of tutors (often on stipend-based contracts) and the difficulty in allocating permanent civil servants (*servidores efetivos*) to support centers are notable (Bizarria, 2014; Silva, 2022). Issues regarding the recognition of teaching work and workload were raised, citing increased time commitment—including weekends—and the lack of regulation of DE as regular work. This situation may lead to health problems and adversely affect private life (Mangueira, 2019; Veloso, 2018). Professional development is insufficient, and the quality of tutoring is compromised by high demand (Chaquime, 2019; Mangueira, 2019; Souza, 2023).

Regarding issues related to funding and the sustainability of DE in institutions, as well as infrastructure, the studies pointed out that financing is a major bottleneck, characterized by dependence on external funding, especially from the UAB System (Barrera, 2018; Chaquime, 2019; Mangueira, 2019; Silva, 2022). Financial sustainability and the inclusion of resources in the core institutional budget were deemed crucial (Moreira, 2021; Silva, 2022). Physical deficiencies were detected in the support centers, which are often organized without adequate planning (Silva, 2013; Silva, 2022).

According to some studies, DE lacks clear and comprehensive institutional policies, frequently operating via disconnected programs and projects (Carbone, 2015; Deus, 2025; Marafante Sá, 2015; Matos, 2016; Souza, 2017). It was observed that excessive bureaucratization and decentralization generate inefficiencies and delays. There is a lack of communication between

sectors and difficulty in streamlining procedures. The modality is poorly understood by administrators, with a tendency to keep UAB courses separate, suffering from political-administrative discontinuity (Melo, 2016; Petter, 2019). Furthermore, an absence of structure and well-defined roles for coordination was indicated.

Other noteworthy aspects—which were not included in the categories listed in Chart 1 because they were not as evident or detailed in the analyzed academic scholarship—include pedagogical issues and those related to instructional materials. Souza (2019) indicated challenges in adapting content and methodology for DE, highlighting that the quality of instructional materials often depends on the professor and can be excessively content-focused. It was also highlighted that dropout rates are a concern, with high attrition attributed to a lack of prior information about the modality, leading students to withdraw when faced with demands similar to those of face-to-face education (Bizarria, 2014; Lordsleem, 2011; Souza, 2023).

5 FINAL REMARKS

The research field regarding the institutionalization of DE is well-established. This study aimed to briefly outline the primary factors that, according to scholarship produced by researchers across the country, hinder the institutionalization process of this modality within Higher Education Institutions. Admittedly, considering the publication dates of the analyzed works, many of the criticisms raised by these researchers may have already been addressed, precisely due to the progress achieved in understanding the importance of institutionalizing an educational modality.

Beyond its inherent significance, the institutionalization of DE stands as a fundamental stage for the involved actors to fully comprehend the modality itself. Thus, it constitutes not merely an administrative or managerial procedure, but rather a truly pedagogical one.

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